

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Togaeva H.U

EROSIVE-ULCER LESIONS OF THE GASTRODUODENAL ZONE IN PATIENTS WITH

LIVER CIRRHOSIS, THEIR DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

TAQDIRLANADI

2023/FEVRAL

